

C ++ ON THE HONORER TEACHER SALARY SYSTEM BASED ON CODE BLOCK

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ABSTRAK

Honorary Teachers are teaching staff who have not been officially recognized by the Government through Employee Numbers or PNS, for this reason Honorary Teachers also have not received salaries like civil servants who already have NIPs. In this study, we will discuss the pattern of the calculation of honorary teacher salaries that are adjusted to the class or level of education and the teaching school with the C ++ programming language which is assisted by the tool Code Block. After doing research, it turns out that C ++ programming language with Code Block software proved to be more effective and efficient in determining Honorary Teacher Salaries.

1. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

Honorary teachers are teachers who have the right to obtain an honorarium, both monthly and national, get legal protection and leave based on government regulations as stipulated in the labor law (Mulyasa, 2016) honorary teachers have less clear employment status, due to contracts that are not determined and the status can be terminated if the contract period has expired,

History with the development of computer media and information technology at this time the work of people's lives is increasing, encouraging one to do and something quickly and easily. In addition, payroll is one of the expenses of a business entity that needs to be managed properly in order to create the right, accurate and fast information. Because payroll is an important factor.

B. Problem Formulation

Based on the background above, describe the welfare of honorary teachers in the region and pay the salaries of honorary teachers

C. Purpose

To fulfill the tasks of algorithm and programming courses

D. Benefits

Easy to calculate the salary of honorary teachers

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Basis of Theory

Honorary teachers are true unsung heroes, meaning honorary teachers are non-permanent teachers who are at least as candidates for Civil Servants, and are paid an hourly lesson. Very often they are paid on a voluntary basis, and even below the officially stipulated minimum salary.

In general, they become volunteers to be appointed as prospective civil servants through honorary channels. Or as a watchman for the opportunity to pass the test for prospective civil servants in general formations.

2.2. Research related

Khurulmitihan, rhadaawiah and hasyimsyari25 "The honorary teacher payroll system uses the concept of agile software development with extreme programming (xp) methodology" STIMIK Lombok Students

By using a payroll or computerized information system, it makes it easier for the treasurer to recapitulate teacher attendance, to streamline treasurer time in calculating teacher salaries because the system will automatically recap absent according to the month entered during the attendance process and using information systems will facilitate the process the achievement of vocational teachers builds the nation.

Chalimatus solikhah "employee attendance and payroll information system at UUD. A glorious wiguna "is an old polytechnic student

Designing attendance and payroll systems at UD. Wiguna is a system design that is expected to be able to handle all current absenteeism and payroll activities, which currently still use manual processes, so the results of the previous discussion can be concluded that: With system design analysis that includes pembuatan diagram flowchart, use case diagrams, context diagrams, ERD (Entity relation diagram)

Employee attendance and payroll system at UD. Wiguna Jaya was successfully designed. The employee attendance and payroll system has been developed with the PHP programming language and MySQL database using open source software, such as LAMP 5.6.3-0, he (diagram editor) and can run on the browser with localhost

Ery murniasih, Edi Wahyudin "Honorary payroll information system to improve the performance of employees in the Middle School 1 middle of the cerbon district farm" after going through the design stage and making the program. Finally, the author can carry out honorary payroll information at Middle School 1 Middle School farmer using the php program. And the following includes:

- a. This program is made as simple as possible so that it can be easily understood for those who want to test the program or make a better application program.
- b. The transaction process is made according to the events that I see in Middle Farmer N1 Middle School.
- c. PHP programming that the author made so that it can help in terms of accuracy and time

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Stages of Research as Following:

- a. Data collection
- b. Initial data processing
- c. Grouping
- d. Stages of the proposed method
- e. Information processing and testing
- f. Research evaluation and validation
- g. Results of research accuracy

The method proposed in this study is C ++ language programming based on Code Blocks to predict HONORER TEACHER SALES at Purbaya Tegal Polytechnic. Steps - steps in research:

1. Calculating the number of hours the teacher teaches
2. Determine the honorarium group
Consisting of 3 groups, namely the Elementary Group, Middle School, and High School Group. Each of them has a different nominal honorarium
3. Calculate teacher salaries
 - a. If the teacher is in the SD class, the calculation of honorarium is obtained from Rp. 15,000 multiplied by the number of teaching hours
 - b. If the teacher includes a junior high school student, the calculation of honorarium is obtained from Rp. 25,000 multiplied by the number of teaching hours
 - c. If the teacher belongs to the Vocational School class, the calculation of honorarium is obtained from Rp.88,000 multiplied by the number of teaching hours
4. Calculating others, among others:
 - a. Primary school transport money is Rp. 2000 = Number of days
And attendance money is IDR 5000 * Number of days
 - b. Middle class transport money is Rp. 3000 = Number of days
And attendance money is IDR 6000 * Number of days
 - c. The transport money for vocational groups is Rp. 3500 = Number of days
And attendance money is Rp. 6500 * Number of days

The following is the program flow:

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data used in this study are data from honorary teachers consisting of elementary, junior high and vocational groups

Table 4.1 datasheets of honorary teachers

NAME	TEACH NUMBER	DAY	CLASS	RESULT
Adhe Nur Meliana S.kom	50	6	SMK	

So, the salary obtained by Adhe Nur Meliana S.kom was Rp.792,000

The following is a salary prediction program for honorary teachers

The following is a payroll program for elementary, junior high school, vocational high school teachers:

```

5 int main()
6 {
7     char namaguru[30], SD, SMP, SMK;
8     int jmlhjam, jmlhhari, honor, transportasi, absensi, totalpendapatan;
9     double gol;
10    cout << "-----" << endl;
11    cout << "          PROGRAM PERHITUNGAN GAJI GURU HONORER          " << endl;
12    cout << "                Oleh : Diki Syaefudin                " << endl;
13    cout << "-----" << endl;
14    cout << " Masukan Nama Guru      : "; cin.getline (namaguru, 30);
15    cout << " Masukan Jumlah Jam Mengajar : "; cin >>jmlhjam;
16    cout << " Masukan Jumlah hari    : "; cin >> jmlhhari;
17    cout << " Masukan Golongan      : "; cin >> gol;
18
19    if (gol==SD){
20        honor=15000*jmlhjam;
21        absensi= 5000*jmlhhari;
22        transportasi=2000*jmlhhari;
23        totalpendapatan=honor+absensi+transportasi;
24        cout << " Guru atas nama " <<namaguru <<" total pendapatan yang diterima " <<totalpendapatan<<endl;

```

Figure 4.1 Opening the code block program

```

21        absensi= 5000*jmlhhari;
22        transportasi=2000*jmlhhari;
23        totalpendapatan=honor+absensi+transportasi;
24        cout << " Guru atas nama " <<namaguru <<" total pendapatan yang diterima " <<totalpendapatan<<endl;
25    } else
26    if (gol==SMP){
27        honor=25000*jmlhjam;
28        absensi= 6000*jmlhhari;
29        transportasi=3000*jmlhhari;
30        totalpendapatan=honor+absensi+transportasi;
31        cout << " Guru atas nama " <<namaguru <<" total pendapatan yang diterima " <<totalpendapatan<<endl;
32    } else
33    if (gol==SMK){
34        honor=88000*jmlhjam;
35        absensi= 6500*jmlhhari;
36        transportasi=3500*jmlhhari;
37        totalpendapatan=honor+absensi+transportasi;
38        cout << " Guru atas nama " <<namaguru <<" total pendapatan yang diterima " <<totalpendapatan<<endl;
39    }
40    return 0;
41 }

```

Figure 4.2 Program calculation in C ++

The following are the results of the honorary teacher payroll program using code :: block by tracing the program and entering the specified text.

```

"C:\Users\Lenovo\Documents\pemrograman gaji honorer\bin\Debug\pemrograman g...
-----
PROGRAM PERHITUNGAN GAJI GURU HONORER
Oleh : Diki Syaefudin
-----
Masukan Nama Guru      : Adhe Nur Meliana, S.kom
Masukan Jumlah Jam Mengajar : 50
Masukan Jumlah hari    : 6
Masukan Golongan      : SMK
Guru atas nama Adhe Nur Meliana, S.kom total pendapatan yang diterima 792000
Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 38.522 s
Press any key to continue.

```

Figure 4.3 Results of the compile program SMK

```
"C:\Users\Lenovo\Documents\pemrograman gaji honorer\bin\Debug\pemrograman g... - □
-----
PROGRAM PERHITUNGAN GAJI GURU HONORER
Oleh : Diki Syaefudin
-----
Masukan Nama Guru      : Dewi yuliani S.pd
Masukan Jumlah Jam Mengajar : 60
Masukan Jumlah hari    : 9
Masukan Golongan       : SD
Guru atas nama Dewi yuliani S.pd total pendapatan yang diterima 963000
Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 31.917 s
Press any key to continue.
```

Figure 4.4 Results of the compile program SD

```
"C:\Users\Lenovo\Documents\pemrograman gaji honorer\bin\Debug\pemrograman g... - □
-----
PROGRAM PERHITUNGAN GAJI GURU HONORER
Oleh : Diki Syaefudin
-----
Masukan Nama Guru      : Toatin S.pd
Masukan Jumlah Jam Mengajar : 55
Masukan Jumlah hari    : 6
Masukan Golongan       : SMP
Guru atas nama Toatin S.pd total pendapatan yang diterima 867000
Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 34.661 s
Press any key to continue.
```

Figure 4.5 Results of the compile program SMP

5. CLOSING

a. Conclusion

Based on the above research using the Code :: block-based C ++ language for salary payments for honorary teachers from elementary, junior high and vocational schools can increase the accuracy of fast and efficient honorary salary calculations.

b. Suggestion

To get the calculation of honorary salaries that is right, accurate and efficient and is better to add C ++ based programs using code :: block

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